
The Main Aspects of Maintaining a Healthy Lifestyle

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Abstract The article reveals the basics of a healthy lifestyle and its norms of formation. The main aspects of maintaining a healthy lifestyle in the "Canon of medical science" Abu Ali Ibn Sina" are analyzed.

Keywords Health, youth education, healthy lifestyle, strategy

Introduction

The greatness of the nation is determined by its origins and traditions going back centuries. Truly Uzbek family embodies the spiritual origins that are passed down from generation to generation and it reflects such outstanding personalities as Beruni and al-Khorazmi, Amir Timur and Ulugbek, Imam al-Bukhori and Ibn Sina, who made a huge contribution to world civilization. Ibn Sina is called one of the founders of the doctrine of health that we today call "healthy lifestyle". The great scientist left invaluable recommendations for preserving health from the period of conception of the fetus, the birth of a child and to old age. His theoretical and practical judgments are based on a deep knowledge of medicine in all age periods of human life.

In Uzbekistan, the issue of educating young people comprehensively healthy and harmoniously developed individuals is in the center of constant attention.

In the modern world, many values that have developed over the centuries are subject to critical evaluation, including the family as a social institution. However, despite certain trends in society, the role of the family in everyone's life is obvious and undeniable. Perhaps it becomes even more important in connection with the need to form the younger generation of sustainable moral values, instilling spirituality and individual responsibility for their choice in a world far from ideal.

The family is the starting point of a person's life and the resource that gives strength to go further, to develop and to overcome inevitable difficulties. But not every family copes with its functions, with its main tasks. All the basic, basic, concepts of the world and of morality a person takes out of his family. Harmonious family relationships, support and acceptance, mutual assistance, high moral values and healthy traditions have a beneficial effect on the younger generation and affect the rest of life.

Medicine and pedagogy bring knowledge to the masses, but without individual interest, without purposeful work of the family, it is impossible to create a healthy society with a Mature and responsible attitude to health as an absolute value. Only the family is able to lay the Foundation of individual health.

Before you give the concept of a healthy lifestyle, we believe it is necessary to determine the essence of health. According to the definition of the world Health Organization, "health is not only the absence of diseases in the physical and mental state, but also the complete social well – being of a person" [1]. Therefore, great attention is paid to the preservation and promotion of health, disease prevention, creation of optimal living conditions. In this regard, the education of a healthy child takes a special place. It depends on the state of health of parents is

determined by the biological nature of man and his heredity. The state pays serious attention to this problem in our country. Even before marriage, the future spouses must determine their health, if necessary, to recover, undergo the necessary treatment, in order to prevent various diseases primarily hereditary underlying factors.

Marriages among relatives, early marriages, bad habits (Smoking, drinking, drug addiction, etc.) have a special place on the health of the future generation. According to the world health organization, more than 60% of children aged 3 to 4 years are diagnosed with health problems. In this regard, the need to form a healthy lifestyle increases, respectively, the issues of preservation and promotion of health become even more urgent. From the very first days of independence, health issues have been Central in Uzbekistan. Based on the recommendations and judgments of the great scientist Ibn Sina and analyzing the achievements of modern medicine, there is a need to create a coherent system of forming the Concept of a healthy lifestyle, the concept of which, unfortunately, for many years had a purely theoretical significance.

In the years of independence of our country successfully carried out the reform of the health care system and one of the priorities is the prevention of diseases, the formation of the philosophy of a healthy lifestyle in the population. Within the framework of the state program "Strategy of actions in five directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" (strategy of actions, 2017) adopted in 2017 and gradually implemented, the scale of activities and projects on education of no one and in no way inferior to youth is expanding. As a result of the work of this program, the implementation of which involved various ministries and departments, institutions, public organizations [2].

Measures to raise a healthy generation have been further improved, and the system of maternal and child health protection has been improved. Comprehensive measures are being taken to further develop children's and youth sports, promote a healthy lifestyle among young people, protect it from the effects of various harmful phenomena. Ibn Sina and modern science consider a healthy lifestyle in terms of spiritual, psychological, physical and medical aspects. Therefore, the system of forming a healthy lifestyle should include all these areas, which requires the development of deep approaches to each of these areas. Another equally important issue is the differentiated approach to the formation of a healthy lifestyle for each age group, starting with a woman's pregnancy and in the subsequent breast, infant, adolescent, young, Mature, elderly and senile ages. Each of these age periods requires a special approach and development of individual recommendations. Only a comprehensive approach, work to expand the medical culture of the population will allow us to cover the broad strata of the population, starting with women's consultations, kindergartens, schools, lyceums, colleges, institutes, enterprises and mahallas. The aim of the study was an in-depth study of the "Canon of medical science" Abu Ali Ibn Sina, which is relevant at the present time. The idea of maintaining health is inherent in the very definition of medicine that Abu Ali Ibn Sina gives: "Health is the ability or condition by which the functions of the organ intended to perform them are impeccable" [3-4].

In his major work "Canon" Ibn Sina gives numerous information about the impact of the environment, lifestyle, diet on the human body and its health. He emphasizes that " ... in medicine it is necessary to know the causes of health and disease ... the causes are of four varieties: material, effective, formal final." The effective reasons included environmental factors, the nature of the air, the quality of food, water, and housing conditions, various stressful conditions, age and sex characteristics, profession and even different habits and customs of people.

Abu Ali Ibn Sina's views on the unity of the organism and the environment, on the dependence of the state of health on their interaction can be clearly seen in the second part and in the third part of the Canon. The scientist repeatedly emphasizes the idea of an individual approach to the protection of human health, because that is useful to one person can be harmful to another. Seven factors must be observed to maintain health. "They are the balance of nature, the choice of food, cleaning the body of excess, maintaining the correct physique, improving what is inhaled through the nose; adaptation of clothing; balance of physical and spiritual movement, the latter includes sleep and wakefulness" [3].

Abu Ali Ibn Sina pays great attention to the issues of nutrition, compliance with the regime of eating, drinking water, especially from streams, physical exercises. The scientist argues that a person moderately timely engaged in physical exercise does not need any treatment, but the exercises should be appropriate for each person. Except for the past ten centuries, it seems that it is written today wisely, consistently, simply.

References

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